

Medial Gastrocnemius Muscle Flap as treatment for coverage of extensive tibial bone exposure associated to post-operative osteosynthesis infection: Case report and review of literature

Rito J. Medellín^{1,2,*}, Aylin M. Del Angel^{2,3}, Alejandro Medina⁴, Antonio D. Rodriguez^{1,2}, Daniel A. Saldaña^{1,2}, Jesus G. Verastegui^{1,2}, Jaime E. Salado^{1,2}

¹Department of General Surgery, Regional High Specialty Hospital “Dr. Ignacio Morones Prieto”, San Luis Potosi, Mexico

²Universidad Autonoma de San Luis Potosi, San Luis Potosi, Mexico.

³Department of Anesthesiology, Regional High Specialty Hospital “Dr. Ignacio Morones Prieto”, San Luis Potosi, Mexico

⁴Department of Plastic Surgery, Regional High Specialty Hospital “Dr. Ignacion Morones Prieto”, San Luis Potosi, Mexico

ABSTRACT

Post-osteosynthesis infections are a common problem most surgeons and orthopedic surgeons deal with on a daily basis, it gets complicated when they affect certain specific body regions or bones, one of the most described is the one affecting the tibial bone and its exposure, for this affection, many treatments are initial options but when all fail, the best is to perform a gastrocnemius muscle flap due to its low failure rates and distant proximally based blood supply that allows these flaps to rotate up to 15 cm above the level of the knee, perfect for proximal tibial defects that both cover the defect and do not limit mobility of the patient.

We describe the case of a 52 year old female, who had a proximal tibia fracture of her left leg and an internal fixator osteosynthesis was performed for proper alignment, two months after surgery she presented with surgical site infection near osteosynthesis material incisions, bone and osteosynthesis material were exposed, causing necrotic tissue and purulent fluid formation. Patient had osteosynthesis material removed in first intervention and an extensive surgical debridement, where a 10cm x 8cm tibial bone exposure was presented. Patient was treated with broad spectrum antibiotics and negative pressure therapy the following 5 months due to E.Coli BLEE present in tissue cultures. Upon negative tissue cultures, it was decided to perform a medial gastrocnemius muscle flap with split thickness skin graft to cover the exposed tibial cutaneous defect. Postoperative outcome was satisfactory, with a 90% integration and no post-op infections were associated.

KEYWORDS: Tibial Exposure, Gastrocnemius Muscle Flap, post-osteosynthesis infection, Tibial Fracture, Negative Pressure Therapy, Surgical site infections

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I. INTRODUCTION

Lower extremity reconstruction surgery in the presence of extensive bone exposure, significant soft tissue loss, or postoperative infection represents a persistent challenge in modern day reconstructive surgery techniques¹. These clinical scenarios, frequently associated with high energy trauma or complications following osteosynthesis fixation procedures, require early, precise, and multidisciplinary surgical interventions that ensure adequate tissue coverage,

promote healing, control infection, and crucially preserve the functionality and mobility of the affected limb^{2,3}.

Among the most widely used regional alternatives, the medial gastrocnemius flap has established itself as a reliable, versatile, and reproducible option for covering defects in the proximal third of the tibia and the peripatellar region^{4,5}. Its constant vascularization, the possibility of mobilization without the need of micro anastomosis, and its ability to incorporate a skin island in selected cases, position it as a first-line tool for reconstructive surgery. However, its use

Medial Gastrocnemius Muscle Flap as treatment for coverage of extensive tibial bone exposure associated to post-operative osteosynthesis infection: Case report and review of literature

requires detailed knowledge of the regional anatomy, meticulous management of neurovascular structures, control of postoperative complications (such as hematomas, infections, flap dehiscence), and adequate surgical planning to ensure flap viability⁶.

The vast papers and literature highlight the high reliability of the medial gastrocnemius muscle as a pedicled flap, making it one of the most widely used due to its technical simplicity and low complication rate⁷. However, its use as a free flap has been rarely reported, despite emerging evidence suggesting adequate results. Its thin fasci, adequate muscle volume, and low donor site morbidity make it ideal for complex reconstructions, traditionally performed in regional settings, but with potential for use in free reconstructions in selected situations⁸.

Despite its advantages, the anatomical limitations of the medial gastrocnemius flap for distal or large defects have prompted the development of alternative surgical procedures. The medial hemi soleus flap has proven effective for the management of mid leg defects, with low morbidity and adequate functional preservation. Furthermore innovative combinations such as composite or chimeric flaps that integrate the medial gastrocnemius muscle with an adipofascial component based on the medial sural artery perforators allow for greater three-dimensional adaptation, expanding its applicability to lateral areas of the affected area and reducing the need for additional grafts.

In recent years, integrated strategies such as the "flap and frame" approach have gained relevance. This technique combines soft tissue reconstruction with simultaneous orthopedical stabilization through external fixation, promoting edema control, rapid healing, and early rehabilitation, with reproducible results even in resource limited surgical settings⁹.

The main indications for the use of gastrocnemius muscle flap are in soft tissue defects of the knee or proximal tibia, particularly when local advancement flaps or simple grafts are not feasible. However, its use should be avoided in cases of severe active infections or extensive bone resections that compromise the viability of the recipient bed, which underscores the need for rigorous preoperative clinical evaluation¹⁰. The technical design involves identifying reliable perforators, lifting the adipofascial component, and reducing the need for skin grafts, thus achieving better aesthetic and functional results¹¹. These techniques have shown a significant reduction in complications such as necrosis, in addition to contributing to effective infection control and acceptable functional recovery¹².

Certain factors such as timing of the surgery, severity of tissue loss, and the number of prior surgeries may influence the outcome, although no statistically significant predictors have been identified so far. The reported rate of infectious

recurrence is approximately 52% while the reimplantation success rates is close to 82%^{13,14}.

Overall the medial and lateral gastrocnemius muscle flap remain safe, well-vascularized, and functional options for covering defects in the knee and proximal tibia¹⁵. The preferential choice of the medial muscle flap is based on its greater volume and length, allowing coverage of defects up to 15cm above the knee joint. Its technical execution requires careful dissection and a precise understanding of the local anatomy, without the need for microsurgery making it especially useful in surgical settings with limited infrastructure^{16,17}. Although complications such as necrosis, infection, or alterations of the extensor mechanism can occur, adequate preoperative evaluation and strict postoperative follow-up are essential to optimize reconstructive results¹⁸.

CASE DESCRIPTION

We present the case of a 52 year old female patient with chronic history for Diabetes and high blood pressure not controlled. She reported regular physical activity, long history of smoking. She had previous surgical intervention for a ventral hernia in 2015 and also C-section in year 2000.

The current condition began with the presence of a proximal tibial diaphyseal fracture in her left leg caused by a fall from own height. Surgery was performed to correct the fracture by implementing internal fixation with titanium plates and screws. During the post operative follow up, surgical site infection was present, purulent exudative liquid was shown and tissue began to have necrosis near surgical site incisions in anterior side of tibia. Due to the presence of pain, erythema and exudative fluid near incision sites, a simple lateral and anteroposterior X-ray was performed during primary care evaluation, where air inside soft tissue was shown near osteosynthesis plates (FIGURE 1,2.), upon closer visual examination the osteosynthesis plate exposure could be observed along de necrotic tissue for which an emergency extensive debridement was performed (FIGURE 3).

Medial Gastrocnemius Muscle Flap as treatment for coverage of extensive tibial bone exposure associated to post-operative osteosynthesis infection: Case report and review of literature

FIGURE 1. Lateral simple X-ray of left leg, we can see de tibial and fibula osteosynthesis plate with screws, presence of gas surrounding soft tissue near the osteosynthesis fixation plate.

FIGURE 2. AP simple X-ray projection of lower left leg,we observe plates and screws in place, presence of gas inside soft tissue.

FIGURE 3. We observe the presence of purulent fluid near osteosynthesis material, alongside necrotic tissue and tibial exposure.

During the surgery, the osteosynthesis plates and screws were removed ,necrotic tissue was resected and an extensive debridement was performed to remove any biofilm that might have developed due to plate exposure, alongside tissue and abscess fluid cultures (FIGURE 4.).

FIGURE 4. We observe the removal of necrotic tissue, observing exposure of tibia and osteosynthesis material, prior to material removal.

Medial Gastrocnemius Muscle Flap as treatment for coverage of extensive tibial bone exposure associated to post-operative osteosynthesis infection: Case report and review of literature

It was decided to start negative pressure therapy (RENASYSS) at a rate of 120mmHg on intermittent setting alongside broad spectrum antibiotics to help with tissue regenerative process, expecting to reduce the cutaneous defect and exudative liquid production on anterior portion of proximal tibial bone which initially measured 10cm x 8cm with bone exposure, an external fixation device was also placed to stabilize the tibial fracture (FIGURE 5.).

FIGURE 5. We observe the external fixation device placed alongside negative pressure therapy in exposure site.

Tissue and fluid cultures reported the presence of E-coli BLEE for which Intravenous Meropenem at a dose of 1.5 gr every 8 hours was indicated for a period of 21 days.

The negative pressure therapy was replaced every 7 days true ambulatory procedure in sterile room, this action was performed for 2 months, granulated tissue was seen surrounding cutaneous defect of around 2mm thickness. Defect area was reduced to 8cm x 8cm with no exudative fluid or necrotic tissue. Upon removal of negative pressure therapy and negative tissue and fluid cultures, it was decided that patient was an adequate candidate for a muscle flap, we observed granulated tissue with no signs of infection (FIGURE 6.).

FIGURE 6. We observe anterior portion of tibia proximal to patella with granulated tissue, exposure zone reduced to half of what was initially exposed, no sign of infection.

Patient was programmed the following day to have a middle gastrocnemius flap and a split thickness skin graft.

Prior to surgical procedure, the medial sural artery was located and marked prior to marking extension of initial incision and muscle flap, a 20 cm incision was made lateral to the tibia, the fascia of the superficial posterior compartment is entered and split true blunt dissection, after which the two heads of the gastrocnemius are observed, the medial head is dissected with its vascular pedicle and the flap is rotated and passed underneath the undermined portion of the original tibial exposure defect, flap is sutured in place with 3-0 prolene, afterwards a full thickness skin graft is placed on top of gastrocnemius muscle flap fixed in place with plastic monocril 3-0 sutures, a tie over is placed to maintain skin graft and muscle graft in close contact (FIGURE 7,8,9,10,11).

Medial Gastrocnemius Muscle Flap as treatment for coverage of extensive tibial bone exposure associated to post-operative osteosynthesis infection: Case report and review of literature

FIGURE 7 . We observe initial lateral incision for gastrocnemius muscle flap, we also observe in lateral portion de original exposure defect.

FIGURE 8. We observe the gastrocnemius flap being rotated underneath the undermined portion of skin to cover the tibial defect.

Medial Gastrocnemius Muscle Flap as treatment for coverage of extensive tibial bone exposure associated to post-operative osteosynthesis infection: Case report and review of literature

FIGURE 9. We observe initial incision for muscle flap, rotation of gastrocnemius muscle under undermined portion and the total area of coverture for this flap.

FIGURE 10. We observe muscle flap being fixed in place with 3-0 prolene suture, covering the total area of exposure.

FIGURE 11. Split-thickness skin graft is placed on top of gastrocnemius muscle flap, initial incision of gastrocnemius flap is sutured with 3-0 prolene.

Medial Gastrocnemius Muscle Flap as treatment for coverage of extensive tibial bone exposure associated to post-operative osteosynthesis infection: Case report and review of literature

After 10 days post-op, the tie over is removed, observing integration of flap and skin graft of 90% with no signs of infection (FIGURE 12.), surgical site is covered with a non adherent gauze.

FIGURE 12. Tie-over removal shows integration of skin graft and muscle flap, no hematoma, no surgical site infection.

DISCUSSION

The medial gastrocnemius flap has historically been the mainstay of reconstructive surgery for cutaneous and coverage defects of the knee and the proximal tibia. Its reliable vascularization, ease of elevation and compatibility along with other techniques, have positioned this flap as the first line of treatment for defects due to trauma, infection, or prosthetic exposure. However, its

limited reach and muscle volume may not be sufficient in larger defects or in the mid and distal regions of the leg.

In this context, the incorporation of the hemisoleus flap as a reconstructive alternative option for defects in the middle third of the tibia represents a high-value reconstructive surgery alternative. This flap when rotated on its pedicle without the need for microanastomosis, maintains ankle function and provides effective muscle coverage to improve vascularization and combat infection. Its use has been validated even in patients at high surgical risk, with satisfactory functional results and minimal postoperative sequelae.

In turn, the use of chimeric flaps that combine the gastrocnemius muscle with adipofascial components based on perforators from the medial sural artery represents a significant advance in the treatment of large defects or those in areas that are difficult to cover. This technique increases the flap mobility, reduces tension, and improves cosmetic results. Combined with temporary external fixation ("flap and frame"), it allows for safer postoperative management, facilitating early mobilization and reducing the risk of necrosis.

Based on the studies and findings, the question remains as to whether the medial gastrocnemius flap should be considered a limb salvage procedure or a definitive solution.

These findings open the door to a new hybrid reconstructive strategy: the planned combination of muscle and adipofascial flaps in a single surgery, without the need for microsurgery, with structured external orthopedic fixation support or osteosynthesis material, which is especially useful in centers or hospitals without the access to advanced plastic surgery treatment. This approach represents not only a technical evolution but also a democratization of access to effective and functional reconstructive surgeries, even in resource-limited settings.

CONCLUSIONS

One of the most common surgical complications after osteosynthesis material placement is its exposure due to surgical site infection. Its treatment can be difficult some times due to the need of removal of the osteosynthesis material and its biofilm.

Nowadays we have access to multiple treatment choices that help reduce treatment time and reduce the need of limb amputation or major surgery debridement.

Soft tissue exposure and tibia exposure benefit from the indication of early negative pressure therapy, followed by placement of partial thickness skin graft and in more complicated cases the use of gastrocnemius muscle flap as an option to cover large areas of cutaneous defect exposure.

Knowing the technique and indications of these type of flaps can be a helpful tool for any surgeon who is

Medial Gastrocnemius Muscle Flap as treatment for coverage of extensive tibial bone exposure associated to post-operative osteosynthesis infection: Case report and review of literature

looking to preserve the integrity of the patients limb among its function and aesthetics.

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